

Supplementary Materials for

Poly(A)-specific RNase (PARN) generates and regulates miR-125a-5p 3'-isoforms, displaying an altered expression in breast cancer

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Supplementary Materials and Methods

Data sources and miRNA isoform annotation

MiRNA-seq (v20) and Paired-end RNA-seq (v32) data were downloaded from 33 TCGA and 5 TARGET cohorts. Further details are available in our previous paper¹.

Cell lines

HEK293 (ATCC; cat. #CRL-1573), MDA-MB-231 (ATCC; cat. #HTB-26), and MDA-MB-436 (ATCC; cat. # HTB-130) were seeded and grown in RPMI-1641 medium (Millipore Sigma, CAT#: R8758) supplemented with 10% of FBS (Millipore Sigma, CAT#: F4135) and penicillin–streptomycin (100 U/mL penicillin and 0.1 mg/mL streptomycin; Millipore Sigma, CAT#: P0781). The authentication of the cell lines was executed through the short-tandem repeat profiling method. Mycoplasma test was regularly performed using the Mycoplasma PCR Detection Kit (Applied Biological Materials) and the MycoAlert™ PLUS Mycoplasma Detection Kit (Lonza).

RNA-binding protein immunoprecipitation (RIP)

For RNA-binding protein immunoprecipitation (RIP), Magna RIP™ RNA-Binding Protein Immunoprecipitation Kit (Millipore Sigma) was employed to process $\sim 3 \times 10^7$ HEK293 cells, following the manufacturer's instructions. RIPAb+Ago2, clone 9E8.2 (Millipore Sigma, CAT#: 03-110) and the corresponding normal mouse IgG, belonging to the same kit, were employed for immunoprecipitation. RNA was purified using UltraPure™ Phenol:Chloroform:Isoamyl Alcohol (25:24:1, v/v) (Thermo Fisher Scientific), quantified with Nanodrop 2000c instrument (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and then analyzed by qRT-PCR using specific Taqman probes as explained in the section “RNA isolation, Reverse transcription, and Real-Time RT-PCR.”

10% of immunoprecipitated samples were diluted in Protein Loading Buffer 2X (Morganville Scientific) and loaded into 4- 12% Criterion™ TGX™ Precast Gels (Bio-Rad). Anti-Argonaute 2 (1:1000 for WB, ABclonal Technology, Cat#: A19709) antibody was used for western blotting analysis.

The normal mouse IgG sample was designated as the negative control, whereas the INPUT sample (representing 10% of the total lysate before immunoprecipitation) was conceived as the positive control.

Differential miRNA isoform expression analysis

Differential expression (DE) analysis was performed considering only TCGA and TARGET cohorts with solid tissues characterized by at least five samples per group (e.g., primary tumor and normal tissues). At first, miRNA isoforms were filtered considering a minimum geometric mean expression >3 RPM in at least one of the two groups (e.g., tumor vs. normal). The resulting expression was further corrected for batch effects, considering standard covariates such as tumor purity and preclinical factors (e.g., gender, age at initial pathologic diagnosis, tumor stage, and platform). Finally, we retained molecules characterized by adjusted P-value <0.05 (Benjamini–Hochberg correction) and $|\text{linear fold change}| >1.5$. Further details are available in our previous paper¹.

Pathway enrichment analysis

To investigate whether miR-125a-5p isoforms could play different roles in breast cancer, we separated TCGA-BRCA patients into two groups: patients with low (below 25th quartile) and high (above 75th quartile) expression of miR-125a-5p (0|0), miR-125a-5p (0|-2), miR-125a-5p (0|-3). Then, gene differential expression analysis was performed considering these two groups (for further information, see Distefano et al.¹), retaining dysregulated genes with adjusted P-value <0.05 and $|\text{linear fold change}| >1.5$. Finally, dysregulated genes were employed to perform a pathway enrichment analysis using the Ingenuity® Pathway Analysis (IPA) software (v01-16). We considered only pathways with $|\text{z-score}| \geq 1.5$ and p-value <0.01 (Supplementary Fig. 2a). For further information, see Distefano et al.¹

Cell lines transfection

HEK293 cells were seeded at 75% of confluence in a 6-well plate two days before the transfection. We transfected 4 µg of the following plasmids: pCMV6-Entry Mammalian Expression Vector (Origene, CAT#: PS100001) as a control, PARN (NM_002582) Human Tagged ORF Clone (Origene, CAT#: RC207220), DIS3L (NM_133375) Human Tagged ORF Clone, (Origene, CAT#: RC201404), TRF4 2 (PAPD5) (NM_001040284) Human Tagged ORF Clone (Origene, CAT#: RC214986), and 100 nM of ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Pool (Horizon Discovery, CAT#: D-001810-10-05), named siCTRL in this paper, and siGENOME Human PARN (5073) siRNA - SMARTpool (Horizon Discovery, CAT#: M-011348-00-005), named siPARN in this paper. The transfection was performed using 4 µL of Lipofectamine™ 2000 Transfection Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, CAT#: 11668027) diluted in RPMI-1641 without FBS and antibiotics. After 5 hours, the transfection medium has been replaced with a complete medium. After 48-72 hours the cells were lysed for RNA or protein extraction.

MDA-MB-231 and MDA-MB-436 cells were seeded at 75% of confluence in a 6-well plate the day before the transfection. We transfected 40 µM of freshly annealed custom RNA oligos (See the section “RNA oligos annealing”) (Integrated DNA Technology) diluted in RPMI-1641 without FBS and antibiotics. After 5 hours, the transfection medium has been replaced with a complete medium. After 72 hours the cells were lysed for protein extraction.

RNA oligos annealing

Custom RNA oligos corresponding to a scramble control and each miR-125a-5p isoform sequence, holding the inverted dT modification at the 3' end, and their complementary and reverse RNA strands were purchased from Integrated DNA Technology:

NC_invdT (negative control):

5'-AUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUinvdT-3'

5'-UAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUA-3'

CAN_invdT (miR-125 (0|0)):

5'-TCCCTGAGACCCTTTAACCTGTGA_{invdT}-3'

5'-TCACAGGTAAAGGGTCTCAGGGA-3'

ISO-2_{invdT} (miR-125 (0|-2)):

5'-TCCCTGAGACCCTTTAACCTGT_{invdT}-3'

5'-ACAGGTAAAGGGTCTCAGGGA-3'

ISO-3_{invdT} (miR-125 (0|-3)):

5'-TCCCTGAGACCCTTTAACCTG_{invdT}-3'

5'-CAGGTAAAGGGTCTCAGGGA-3'

For the annealing reaction, 5 μ L of 100 μ M stock dilution of each strand were mixed in equal molar amount with 2.5 μ L of 5X Annealing Buffer (10 mM Tris pH 7.5, 1 mM EDTA, 50 mM NaCl), then heated for five minutes at 95°C, and progressively cooled to 25°C with a lowering of temperature of 0.5°C every 18 seconds. After two further minutes at 25°C, they were stored at -20°C for a long term (within 24 hours) or in ice until use.

Protein lysis and Western Blotting

Cells were lysed in Lysis buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, 10% Glycerol) supplemented with Protease inhibitors (Millipore Sigma). 30 μ g of proteins, mixed with Protein Loading Buffer 1X (Morganville Scientific), run onto 4- 12% Criterion™ TGX™ Precast Gels (Bio-Rad) at 200 V, 50-100mA, for about one hour and then transferred with the Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System (Bio-Rad) on nitrocellulose membranes (GE Healthcare Life Science). After one hour shaking in blocking solution (TBS-0.05% Tween®20/fat-free milk 5%), membranes were incubated overnight at 4°C with primary antibodies: anti-CCNE2 (1:1000 for WB, Cell Signaling, Cat#: 4132), anti-CDK2 (1:1000 for WB, Cell Signaling, clone 78B2, Cat#: 2546), anti-CDK6 (1:1000 for WB, Cell Signaling, clone DCS83, Cat#: 3136), anti-PARN (1:1000 for WB, ABclonal Technology, Cat#: A6941), anti-DIS3L (1:1000 for WB, ABclonal Technology, Cat#: A16160), anti-PAPD5 (1:1000 for WB, ABclonal Technology, Cat#: A15885), anti-Argonaute 2 (1:1000 for WB, ABclonal Technology, Cat#: A19709), anti-Beta-Actin (1:2000 for WB, Cell

Signaling, clone 13E5, Cat#: 4970), and anti-Vinculin (1:10000 for WB, Abcam Cat#: 18058), diluted in TBS-0.05% Tween®20/fat-free milk 3-5% or TBS-0.05% Tween®20/BSA 5%. After the O/N incubation, membranes have undergone three washes with TBS-0.05% Tween®20 (TBS-T) (Bio-Rad) and incubated with HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies, Rabbit IgG HRP Linked Whole Ab (from Donkey) (1:5000 for WB, Millipore Sigma Cat#: NA934) or Mouse IgG HRP Linked Whole Ab (1:5000 for WB, Millipore Sigma Cat#: NA931), for one hour at room temperature. After three additional washes, membranes were assayed with ECL (Millipore Sigma), and the signal was marked and developed on Blue X-ray films (GeneMate) inside a dark room.

Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis was performed leveraging the TCGA-BRCA expression data (solid primary tumor samples) generated in our previous work¹. MiRNA isoforms and genes were initially filtered using a minimum geometric mean expression >3 RPM and >1 Transcripts Per Million (TPM), respectively, and then the expression was corrected for batch effects (tumor purity). Finally, the Spearman correlation was applied to calculate significance and correlation coefficients.

Mutagenesis of PARN

The plasmid PARN (NM_002582) Human Tagged ORF Clone (Origene, CAT#: RC207220) underwent a mutagenesis step to replace the 28th amino acid (Aspartate) with Alanine, thus affecting one of the four catalytic sites of this protein. PARN-D28A is an inactive 3'-5' exonuclease but it still retains the ability to bind the RNA. The mutagenesis was performed using QuickChange II XL Site-Directed Mutagenesis Kit (Agilent Technologies, CAT#:200521-5) following the manufacturer's instructions.

The mutagenesis primers were designed using the QuikChange Primer Design tool (agilent.com/store/primerDesignProgram.jsp):

PARN_D28A_Fw 5'-GACTTCTTCGCCATCGCTGGGGAGTTTTTCAGGA-3'

PARN_D28A_Rv 5'-TCCTGAAAAC TCCCCAGCGATGGCGAAGAAGTC-3'

The mutated plasmid was subsequently subjected to Sanger sequencing to verify mutagenesis.

RNA isolation, reverse transcription, and real-time RT-PCR

Total RNA was isolated from cells 72 hours after the transfection using TRIzol™ Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's protocol and measured with the Nanodrop 2000c instrument (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The expression of the three miR-125a-5p isoforms was assessed by real-time RT-PCR using TaqMan® Small RNA Assays (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and normalized using RNU44 as a control. 5 ng of total RNA were employed for a reverse-transcription specific for each small RNA, which was performed using the High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific), 30 min 16°C, 30 min 42°C, 5 min 85°C, and TaqMan® Small RNA Assays RT-primers (Thermo Fisher Scientific) from the assays listed below. The real-time RT-PCR was completed using TaqMan™ Fast Advanced Master Mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific), according to the standard protocol, employing the cataloged TaqMan® Small RNA Assays listed below:

miR-125a-5p (0|0): (Assay ID: 002198)

miR-125a-5p (0|-2): (Assay ID: 007065)

miR-125a-5p (0|-3): (Assay ID: 474061)

RNU44 (control): (Assay ID: 001094)

Immunoprecipitation

The antibody anti-DDK (FLAG) (1:200 for IP, Origene, clone OTI4C5, CAT#: TA50011) or normal mouse IgG (4 µg for IP, Millipore Sigma, CAT#: 12-371) were added to 50 µL of Protein A/G PLUS Agarose beads (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, CAT#: sc-2003), previously washed once in cold TBS 1X (Bio-Rad) and once in cold protein lysis buffer, and incubated together for one hour at 4°C with gentle rocking. Then, after two further washes with protein lysis buffer, beads bound to the antibody or mouse IgG were added to 1 mg of protein lysates from cells previously transfected for 48 hours with PARN (NM_002582) Human Tagged ORF Clone (holding the DDK sequence) and incubated again O/N at 4°C with gentle rocking. The

day after, beads were washed twice with cold protein lysis buffer and once with cold TBS 1X, resuspended in Protein Loading Buffer 2X (Morganville Scientific) supplemented with 10% of 2-Mercaptoethanol (Millipore Sigma), denatured at 95°C for 10 minutes and subject to Western Blotting.

Northern Blotting

25 µg of RNA isolated from cells and quantified as described above (See section “RNA isolation, reverse transcription, and real-time RT-PCR”) were mixed 1:1 with NOVEX® TBE-Urea Sample Buffer (2X) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, CAT#: LC6876) and denatured at 70°C for 10 minutes. Then, denatured RNAs were loaded onto 15% TBE-Urea Gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, CAT#: EC6885BOX) and subject to electrophoresis at 150 V, in TBE 1X (National Diagnostic), for about two hours. A microRNA Marker (New England BioLabs, CAT#: N2102S) was used according to the manufacturer’s instructions to assess the molecular weight of the miR-125a-5p isoforms. After the run, the gel was stained with Ethidium Bromide (Bio-Rad), diluted at the concentration of 0.5 µg/mL in TBE 1X, to check the RNA quality and then subject to electroblotting. The samples were transferred to a positive charged nylon membrane, Hybond™ -N⁺ (GE Healthcare) in cold TBE 1X, at 360 mA, for three hours. After the transfer, the membrane underwent crosslinking of RNA through ultraviolet light and then has been incubated with ULTRAhyb™ Ultrasensitive Hybridization Buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, CAT#: AM8670) at 42°C, with gentle rocking for 30 minutes. Then, 5’ dual biotin-labeled probes (Integrated DNA Technologies), complementary to miR-125a-5p, miR-15a-5p, RNU6B, and microRNA marker (See sequences listed below), were added to the Hybridization buffer with a final concentration of 10 nM for microRNAs and RNU6B probes and 0.1 nM for the microRNA marker probe. After two O/N incubations with probes, the signal was detected using Chemiluminescent Nucleic Acid Detection Module (Thermo Fisher Scientific, CAT#: 89880), according to the manufacturer’s instructions.

Northern Blotting probes:

miR-125a-5p: 5’- /52-bio/ AGGTAAAGGGTCTCAGGGA - 3’

miR-15a-5p: 5’- /52-bio/ CAAACCATTATGTGCTGCTA - 3’

RNU6B (control): 5' - /52-bio/ GTGCTGCCGAAGCGAGCAC- 3'

microRNA marker: 5' - /52-bio/ AGGTAAAGGGTCTCAGGGA- 3'

References of Supplementary Materials

1. Distefano, R. *et al.* Pan-Cancer Analysis of Canonical and Modified miRNAs Enhances the Resolution of the Functional miRNAome in Cancer. *Cancer Research* **82**, 3687–3700 (2022).

Supplementary figures

Supplementary Fig.1 miR-125a-5p 3' end isoforms in breast cancer

a. Sequences of the nine miR-125a-5p 3' end isoforms without sequence modifications significantly dysregulated in 17 patients' cancer cohorts belonging to The Cancer Genome Atlas Program (TCGA) and

The Therapeutically Applicable Research to Generate Effective Treatments (TARGET). The significance was assessed considering a geometric mean >3 RPM in at least one group (normal or cancer), with a $|\text{linear FC}| > 1.5$ and an FDR < 0.05 . (See Supplementary material and methods). The data were normalized taking into account covariates such as tumor purity, pathologic stages, and age at initial pathologic diagnosis. In red are the isoforms studied in this project. **b.** Expression (CPM) in TCGA-BRCA cohort of the four miR-125a-5p 3' end isoforms presenting an expression above the 25th percentile of the miR-125-5p 3' -isoforms expression in all the comparisons. **c.** Expression of miR-125a-5p isoforms in different breast cancer subtypes. The samples belong to the TCGA-BRCA cohort (88 normal, 990 breast cancer patients). The statistical significance was assessed using a Kruskal-Wallis H-test. ****P < 0.0001 .

Supplementary Fig.2 miR-125a-5p 3' end isoforms functional analysis

a. RNA-immunoprecipitation experiments have proven that AGO2 is loaded with all the three miR-125a-5p present in this study. The statistical significance was assessed using a two-tailed Student's t-test. **b.** Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) performed on genes differentially expressed in breast cancer patients presenting higher or lower expression of miR-125a-5p (0|0), miR-125a-5p (0|-2), and miR-125a-5p (0|-3) respectively. **c.** The IPA analysis stemmed from the DE analysis (b) suggests an involvement of the isoforms mir-125a (0|-2) and mir-125a (0|-3) in the regulation of the cell cycle. The graphs show three significantly dysregulated pathways following the upregulation of these two isoforms. **d.** Custom RNA duplex oligos designed for the study of miR-125a-5p 3' end isoforms functional role. An inverted dT has been added at the 3' end of each 5'-3' strand of the duplex (CTRL included) to prevent the degradation mediated by 3'-5' exonucleases. The sequence AUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAUAU_invdT was used as scramble control. **e.** Western blotting analysis shows the downregulation of CCNE2, CDK2, and CDK6 in the presence of an upregulation mir-125a (0|-2) and mir-125a (0|-3) due to the 72h transfection of custom RNA duplex oligos (**panel d**) with a modification at the 3' end that inhibits the 3'-5' exonucleases degradation, in MDA-MB-231 and MDA-MB-436 triple-negative breast cancer cell lines. The sample names represent the duplex oligos corresponding to each miR-125a-5p isoform (see Supplementary Materials and Methods, section "RNA oligos annealing"). ***P < 0.001.

a

Supplementary Fig.3 Role of exonucleases in miR-125a-5p 3' end isoforms generation and stability

a. Western blotting on HEK293 cells displays the expression of wild-type PARN and the inactive mutant PARN D28A proteins after transfection of 4 μ g of plasmids holding the ORF coding for these proteins. pCMV6-Entry Mammalian Expression Vector has been used as a control. The arrow indicates the specific band corresponding to PARN in both endogenous and exogenous forms. **b.** qRT-PCR experiments, performed using TaqMan probes specific for each isoform, confirmed the trimming of miR-125a-5p (0|0) mediated by PARN wild-type. The upregulation of this exonuclease in HEK293 cells correlates with an increased expression of the two miR-125a-5p sculpted isoforms, miR-125a-5p (0|-2) and miR-125a-5p (0|-3). The statistical significance was assessed using a two-tailed Student's t-test. **c.** Expression of endogenous protein PARN in HEK293 cells after transfection with a siRNA against PARN (siPARN). A siRNA scramble has been used as a control (siCTRL). The arrow indicates the specific band corresponding to the endogenous PARN. **d.** Northern blotting analysis was performed to assess the expression of the endogenous miR-125a-5p after the downregulation of PARN. RNU6B has been used as a control. **e.** Immunoprecipitation experiments carried out on HEK293 transfected for 48h with PARN (NM_002582) Human Tagged ORF Clone (Myc-DDK-tagged) demonstrated that PARN belongs to the same protein complex of AGO2 and PAPD5. The immunoprecipitations were performed using an antibody against the DDK (FLAG) sequence and normal mIgG as negative control. **f.** Western blotting analysis shows the expression of PARN, DIS3L, and PAPD5 after 72-hour transfection of a siRNA against PARN (siPARN) and 4 μ g of plasmids holding the ORF coding for DIS3L and PAPD5. Beta actin (BACT) has been used as a control. **g.** qPCR of transcription inhibition time course using 5 μ g/mL of Actinomycin D in HEK293 cells. FOXO3 has been used as a control since it is a short-lived transcript. FOXO3 expression data were normalized using a stable transcript, GAPDH. **h.** Western Blotting experiment shows the expression of PARN and DIS3L after 72h transfection using plasmids holding the ORF coding for PARN and DIS3L. Beta actin (BACT) has been used as a control. **i.** qRT-PCR experiments, performed using TaqMan probes specific for DIS3L (Assay: Hs00900784_m1) and PARN (Assay ID: Hs01105410_m1), confirmed the

transfection of PARN (NM_002582) Human Tagged ORF Clone (Origene, CAT#: RC207220), and DIS3L (NM_133375) Human Tagged ORF Clone, (Origene, CAT#: RC201404) in HEK293 cells after 72 hours.

*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001.